

Anti-Corruption Education as a Prevention of Criminal Acts of Corruption

ABSTRACT

The high number of corruption cases in Indonesia requires schools to play an active role in instilling the values of integrity and motivating students to participate in efforts to prevent and eradicate criminal acts of corruption. This research was conducted to analyze efforts of preventing and eradicating about criminal acts of corruption through anti-corruption education in schools. The research was carried out in a normative juridical manner using qualitative descriptive analytical methods. The results of the research are that Anti-Corruption Education for school students provides motivation in efforts to prevent criminal acts of corruption through guidance on values education, namely good values. The Anti-Corruption Education learning model also needs to be an interesting subject and not monotonous. The material presented must strengthen cognitive aspects, and choosing creative learning methods is the key to success by optimizing students' intellectual, critical nature and ethical integrity, in which competent educators can fulfill roles as communicators, facilitators, and motivators.

Keywords : Anti-Corruption Education , Values, Preventing and Eradicating Corruption

INTRODUCTION

Corruption in Indonesia has become a chronic disease that is difficult to be healed. Even though we often encounter anti-corruption slogans, sometimes they feel like empty talk. Neglect, whether intentional or not, by the Indonesian people has further exacerbated this situation. Corruption is difficult to prevent and eradicate because behavior is considered normal and beneficial to oneself or others. According to Transparency International, Indonesia ranked 115th out of 180 countries in terms of corruption levels in 2023, with the same score as in 2022, indicating that corruption in Indonesia is still high compared to the global average.ⁱ Corruption in Indonesia seems to have become a disturbing industry. Our country is always ranked at the top as one of the most corrupt countries.ⁱⁱ This fact indicates that the level of corruption in Indonesia is very high. Therefore,

concrete efforts are needed to reduce the increasing rate of corruption in the country.

Corruption, in its simplest terms, refers to the misuse of power for personal benefit. This definition encompasses the actions of public officials—both politicians and civil servants—who inappropriately enrich themselves and violate the law. It also includes individuals close to bureaucratic officials who abuse the authority entrusted to them.ⁱⁱⁱ In Indonesian vocabulary, corruption is commonly associated with illicit acts such as embezzlement and accepting bribes.^{iv}

Corruption in Indonesia has undergone various prevention and eradication efforts since 1999, when Law Number 31 of 1999 *jo* . UU no. 20 of 2001 concerning Corruption Crimes was issued. The pattern of the anti-corruption system in Indonesia shows that the eradication of corruption has been carried out substantially and structurally through the establishment of anti-corruption laws and institutions. The two approaches used are criminal law enforcement using criminal law instruments to deal with crime, as well as preventive non-criminal justice which is integrated in culture and systematic patterns. Even though several programs have succeeded in eradicating corruption, such as the anti-corruption canteen program, there are still challenges in instilling an anti-corruption attitude in society, especially among the millennial generation.^v

Anti-corruption education is a learning process that aims to instill the values of integrity, honesty and openness in students. In this way, they can avoid, prevent and reject corrupt practices. This approach involves educational institutions from the lowest level of education to tertiary institutions . The aim is to create a generation that is legally aware, committed to the principles of truth, honesty and justice.^{vi} By strengthening these values, we move towards political renewal and creating a good culture, as well as encouraging the realization of responsible government in educational units.

Anti-Corruption education provided to students at the school level is an effort to motivate students to participate in preventing acts of corruption so that

they don't be a corruptor. The participation of students in anti-corruption efforts is not primarily about law enforcement actions carried out by official institutions. Instead, it emphasizes how students can actively prevent corruption and contribute to eradicating corrupt practices. By fostering an anti-corruption culture and focusing on prevention, students play a crucial role in combating corruption, especially in the areas where they live. Students are expected to act as agents of change and driving forces for the Anti-Corruption movement in society. Hence, in order to serve as change agents and actively contribute to fostering an anti-corruption culture, students must receive adequate knowledge about the purpose and scope of anti-corruption efforts, as well as effective strategies for prevention and eradication. Furthermore, a critical aspect involves motivating students to prevent corruption, fostering their understanding, and enabling the application of anti-corruption values in their daily lives as responsible members of society, the nation, and the state.

The objective of Anti-Corruption education for school students is to equip them with comprehensive knowledge about the various aspects of corruption, strategies for prevention, and eradication methods. Additionally, it aims to instill anti-corruption values. The ultimate goal of providing Anti-Corruption Education is to cultivate an anti-corruption culture among students and encourage their active participation in combatting corrupt practices.^{vii} According to description, the aim of the research is to analyze efforts to prevent and eradicate criminal acts of corruption through anti-corruption education in schools.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used normative juridical approach. Furthermore, this research is not only conceptualized around all the principles and rules that regulate patterns of social behavior and human life in society, but also collects material from an external perspective using qualitative methods to draw conclusions about the relationship between legal rules and reality. The specifications in this research are analytical descriptive.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cause Factors

The cause of corruption which is common in Indonesia is because there are people who think that if you get wealth, you can be successful. That is why people use all means to obtain wealth, which through corruption causes losses to the nation and state.^{viii} The following are several factors that cause criminal acts of corruption, namely:

a. Human Personal Factors.

The main cause of corruption is the root of greed, if society's attitude is materialistic and the form of politics still depends on material things alone, which can encourage corruption and money politics. At that time, it is likely that many government officials will become corrupt. If the desire to become rich can no longer be controlled while wealth can be obtained through corruption, then corruption is easy to do. A consumerist lifestyle without a decent income can create opportunities for corruption in fulfilling these consumerist demands. People who commit corruption because of greed and materialistic attitudes must be dealt with firmly. Lack of faith and morality makes a person easily attracted to a consumerist lifestyle, greed and excessive desire for wealth, which leads to corruption.^{ix}

b. Family and Community Factors.

The encouragement to commit corruption can come from other people or from society which provides opportunities to do so. These external factors can be explained as follows: First, corrupt behavior may be motivated by family incentives. According to the behavioral school, social and social are often the biggest drivers in carrying out these actions. In fact, family factors often offer protection rather than punishment for family members who abuse the authority of family members who abuse special authority in corruption cases. Second, a person is motivated to commit corruption because society is full of corrupt cultures, beliefs and values. Corrupt habits can give rise to corruption. Third, there is a lack of public awareness that the people themselves are the main victims of corruption.

c. Economic and Political Factors.

Politically, social control is a process that must be implemented so that not everyone commits corruption as society expects. This social control is carried out through the assumption of various functions by politically organized state institutions and NGOs. Weak social control over corruption allows corrupt practices to grow freely in society.

d. Organizational Factors.

The existence of an organizational culture can create corruption and have a big impact on its members. Thus, if organizational culture is difficult to manage well, it can cause unfavorable conditions in an organization. Aspects of an organization can contribute to corruption themselves. Firstly, supervisors or managers lack exemplary behavior. A leadership position in an institution has a tremendous impact on its subordinates. Therefore, if leaders have not been able to set a good example to their subordinates regarding corruption, it is very likely that they will do the same thing, and secondly, there is a lack of organizational responsibility.

The Importance of Anti-Corruption Education

Basically, Anti-Corruption Education is a step to prevent corruption started by implementing anti-corruption values in every person, especially for school children as young people who have the responsibility to lead the country's future.^x Anti-Corruption Education can be understood as a conscious and systematic way to equip young people with the values, knowledge and skills needed so that they can prevent the possibility of corruption from occurring.

The 2005 Anti-Corruption Education organized by the Lithuanian Ministry of Education shows that the main task of this training is to equip students with an understanding of how to distinguish other crimes from corruption crimes, where the general aim of Anti-Corruption Education is the formation of information regarding the forms and aspects of corruption, changes in behavior and concepts. regarding corruption, developing skills and the ability

to eradicate it. Schools should consider various aspects related to anti-corruption education. This is a goal to be achieved, these aspects are:

a. Knowledge about corruption.

This knowledge is very much needed, for example information related to acts of corruption, including information that can produce young people who can correctly differentiate criminal acts of corruption from other criminal acts. The causes and effects of corruption is one of the knowledge that must be conveyed. Then young people also have a clear opinion regarding why corruption is considered a bad act that must be avoided, and analyze the causes and impacts of corruption in various areas of life.

b. Attitude progress.

Anti-Corruption Education can also develop young people's behavior, such as character and value education, where attitude is a person's desire to assess an object through their behavior based on emotional information.

c. Behavioral transformation.

Changing behavior that has existed for a long time is not easy, and this behavior is the opposite of the behavior expected by teaching staff, for example cheating on tests at school which often occurs among students.

d. Moral Perspective.

Morally good or bad actions can be identified from their impact, whether the action disturbs or causes harm to other people, the action can also be recognized from its intention.

Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education Values as Early as Possible in the School Environment

Anti-Corruption Education materials should incorporate essential anti-corruption values, including attitudes, core principles, and ethical norms. These values, developed by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), encompass honesty, compassion, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, courage, and justice. Anti-corruption education primarily focuses on

preventing corruption by instilling these values in individuals, particularly schoolchildren—the future leaders of our nation. At least nine anti-corruption values should be instilled in students from an early age, namely:

a. Honesty.

An honest attitude in everyday life is the starting point for preventing corruption. People who implement an honest attitude direct themselves to stay away from corrupt attitudes, because they are afraid of disappointing other people. Apart from harming other parties, the result of being dishonest is psychological pressure that is felt over a certain period of time. For example, anti-corruption initiatives that reflect these values are doing the work that should be done, don't copy or duplicate other people's work, don't manipulate information and facts, and always be wise in making decisions. Do the work that should be done, don't copy or duplicate other people's work, don't manipulating information and facts in the workplace, being wise and judicious in making decisions.^{xi}

b. Care.

Caring means paying attention, paying attention, ignoring. A caring attitude can be applied to the environment around us and things that develop within it, for example caring for the surrounding environment, both family, school and community.

c. Independence.

Being independent means being able to stand on one's own feet, meaning not depending much on other people in various matters. The value of independence can be realized in the form of doing exam questions independently, carrying out all responsibilities with one's own efforts and not someone else's.

d. Discipline.

The term 'discipline' originates from the Latin word '*disciplina*,' which encompasses training, education in politeness and spirituality, and character development. Discipline finds expression in various ways, including effective time management, adherence to rules and regulations, timely completion of tasks, and maintaining focus on work.

e. Responsibility.

The definition of the word responsibility according to Sugono is the condition of having to bear everything (if something happens, you can be sued, blamed and sued). When viewed from an individual's condition regarding the relationships they make, responsibility is divided into 5 types, namely responsibility towards oneself, responsibility towards family, responsibility towards society, responsibility towards the nation and state and responsibility towards God.

f. Hard work.

Hard work denotes persistent effort, characterized by unwavering commitment to completing assigned tasks. It transcends mere completion and instead embodies a grand vision aimed at benefiting both humanity and the environment.

g. Simple.

Lifestyle is something that is very important for interactions with the surrounding community. With a simple lifestyle, humans are accustomed to not living extravagantly, not according to their abilities. With a simple lifestyle, a person is also trained to prioritize needs above desires.

h. Brave.

A courageous attitude can be shown by being brave in telling or defending the truth, daring to take responsibility, admitting mistakes made, and so on. Courage is very important in achieving success, and courage can also be greater if it is followed by a confident attitude, then confidence will mature if you have strong knowledge.

i. Justice.

Justice means giving something equally, for example an anti-corruption attitude that reflects this value is giving other people the rights they should have, not acting fraudulently such as taking other people's shares, carrying out work given to them before they get their rights, taking steps without taking sides or doing something. things that help the element of nepotism.

It has been explained that there are 9 values that have been classified by KPK, and are the implementation of anti-corruption training in schools, where these values have existed for a long time which are clearly reflected in the nation's Pancasila view of life, but with the modernization of mobility related to globalization, consumer culture started to collapse. In Indonesia itself, corruption cases cannot disappear but instead often occur through more complex modern modes. Thus, it is important for us to have methods and patterns that are able to prevent and awaken the people and government to participate in each other to eradicate this. Apart from that, preventing and eradicating corruption has essentially become the task of the Indonesian people whose sector has been proven to implement repressive anti-corruption enforcement through the implementation of the Corruption Crime Law, the establishment of a forum for preventing and eradicating corruption, namely KPK.^{xii} The most appropriate and effective way to eradicate corruption is through educational media, and that starts with basic education. Creating a new curriculum regarding the anti-corruption curriculum is a step to eradicate corruption through formal education in educational institutions.^{xiii}

The Role of Students in the Anti-Corruption Movement

Student engagement in the Anti-Corruption movement can be grounded in four key domains, namely:

a. Family environment

The family environment serves as a crucial litmus test for students to assess the internalization of anti-corruption values. The process of instilling anti-corruption character in students begins with observing the daily conduct of family members.^{xiv}

From this context, one can discern the level of adherence to applicable rules. Violating these rules harms others by infringing upon their rights—an antecedent to corrupt behavior. However, this process is challenging due to the inherent bias when observing family members, who are the

closest and most frequently encountered individuals.^{xv} For instance, how can a child reprimand a parent who routinely flouts traffic regulations? Does the child dare to inquire about the source of their parents' income? Or criticize other family members for using pirated goods? The values parents impart within the family environment persist throughout a student's life. Successfully navigating this complexity fosters resilience, enabling students to confront societal obstacles that may lead to corrupt acts. By instilling anti-corruption education in many (if not all) school students, Indonesia can cultivate a substantial cohort of young individuals committed to combating corruption.

b. School environment

Participation in the anti-corruption movement within the school environment is intrinsically linked to students' roles as active participants in realizing their school's vision and mission. Student involvement in this movement encompasses two distinct areas: individual commitment and collective engagement within the student community.

Within the individual context, students are expected to refrain from engaging in corrupt behavior. In the community context, their responsibility extends to preventing corruption within their peer groups and student organizations. To effectively contribute to the anti-corruption movement, students must exemplify both anti-corruption and ethical conduct across various levels. Acquiring anti-corruption values and understanding the principles of corruption and anti-corruption can be facilitated through participation in socialization activities, campaigns, seminars, and Anti-Corruption Education programs. It is essential that students apply these values and knowledge in their daily lives, demonstrating their commitment to integrity and distancing themselves from corrupt practices.

Diverse activities can be implemented to instill anti-corruption values within the student community and student organizations, fostering an anti-corruption culture.^{xvi} These activities may include campaigns, outreach programs, seminars, and educational initiatives. For instance, organizing a clean exam or anti-cheating campaign can promote values

such as hard work, honesty, responsibility, and independence. Additionally, real-world examples like the 'honesty canteen' demonstrate practical ways to cultivate honesty and responsibility in everyday life.

c. Community Environment

Student engagement in anti-corruption movements within society extends to students or student groups actively observing their surrounding community environment.

d. Local and National Environment

Student engagement in advocating against corruption at local and national levels is grounded in their status as citizens with equal rights and responsibilities. At these levels, student involvement in the anti-corruption movement aims to prevent widespread and systematic corrupt practices within society. Leveraging their competencies, students can emerge as leaders in local and national anti-corruption efforts. Commencing with organized activities within schools, students propagate anti-corruption norms to the broader community, initially within the school vicinity and subsequently expanding their impact. These collaborative and ongoing anti-corruption initiatives serve to raise public awareness and foster determination to combat corruption in the Republic of Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

According to discussion, it can be concluded as follows. First, anti-corruption education for school students aims to prevent and eradicate criminal acts of corruption by instilling essential values. This education fosters a sense of embarrassment when faced with temptation to engage in corrupt behavior and invokes anger upon witnessing alleged corruption. The fundamental moral attitudes that immunize individuals against the lure of corruption include honesty, compassion, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, courage, and justice.

Second, given the alarming prevalence of corruption in Indonesia across various demographics, including students, designing an engaging and non-monotonous Anti-Corruption Education learning model presents challenges. The instructional material plays a crucial role in enhancing cognitive aspects. Employing creative teaching methods is essential for optimizing students' intellectual capacity, critical thinking, and ethical integrity. Effective teachers serve as communicators, facilitators, and motivators. Additionally, school leaders play a vital role in establishing a strong foundation and supporting the effectiveness of Anti-Corruption Education.

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